

Study of Vibrational, Mechanical and Dielectrical Properties of ADP Single Crystal

T. Mahalakshmi, R.Kiruthiga, S.Sujatha, R. Nirmal Kumar* and R. Thiyagarajan

PG and Research Department of Physics, Srimad Andavan Arts & Science College, Trichy

Corresponding Author: *nirmal@andavancollege.ac.in* (90436 18722)

Abstract

Several research works have been carried out on pure and doped ADP crystals, because of its unique non-linear optical, dielectric, antiferroelectric and piezoelectric properties [1]. Moreover, it was the first material that were used and exploited for their non-linear optical and electro-optic properties [2]. Here, With an aim of finding new useful materials for academic and industrial use, an attempt has been made to grow the single crystals of ADP using the salt water as solvent. The crystalline nature and various planes of reflections were studied using Powder X-ray diffraction analysis. The Presence of functional groups in the grown crystal was identified using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy. Vicker's microhardness test was employed to study the mechanical strength of the grown crystal. The variation of Vickers hardness with applied load indicates that the crystal exhibit Reverse Indentation Size Effect (RISE). The grown crystal has soft nature confirmed from Meyer's law. Dielectric properties such as dielectric constant and dielectric loss were studied as function of frequency for varying temperature. The low dielectric loss at higher frequency implies that grown crystal has good optical quality and lesser defects.

Keywords: ADP, RISE, Dielectric property, mechanical strength.

Reference

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